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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF CATIONIC SUBMICRON EMULSION FOR ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUG DELIVERY

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the potential of cationic submicron emulsion as a colloidal drug delivery system for poorly-soluble Loteprednol etabonate in keratoconjunctivitis sicca (dry eye syndrome). Cationic submicron emulsion was formulated and optimized by preparation of a preemulsion followed by final emulsion by using a combined approach of mixing and heating. Labrafac Lipophile WL 1349; a Medium chain triglyceride was used as oil phase, Oleylamine as cationic lipid system and Cremaphor EL, Solutol HS 15 and Hydroxy Propyl methyl cellulose were used as the stabilizer surfactant systems. 0.2% w/w Loteprednol etabonate drug was incorporated in the optimised emulsion and the emulsion was high speed homogenised. The cationic submicron emulsion was evaluated for its pH, globule size, viscosity, zeta potential, osmolarity, drug content, stability and anti-inflammatory efficacy in moderate evaporative dry eye rabbit models against marketed eyedrops; Loteflam®(0.5% w/w Loteprednol etabonate). A stable cationic submicron emulsion containing 0.2% w/w Loteprednol etabonate with pH 7.22, globule size of 978 nm, viscosity of 2.41 cps, zeta potential of + 67.4 mV, osmolarity of 286 milliOsms, drug content of 94% was obtained which was found to have comparable anti-inflammatory efficacy as marketed Loteflam® (0.5% w/w Loteprednol etabonate) eye drops at a lower drug concentration when evaluated in moderate evaporative dry eye rabbit models. Conclusion: High speed homogenisation was found to yield a stable cationic submicron emulsion exhibiting anti-inflammatory efficacy comparable to marketed formulation but at lower concentration in keratoconjunctivitis sicca.

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INTRODUCTION

Topical drug delivery to ophthalmic pathologies like Keratoconjunctivitis sicca (Dry eye syndrome) and other corneal disorders exhibits several challenges. Solutions and suspensions are the most commonly used formulations for topical ophthalmic disorders.[1] Recently ointments have also been explored to treat ophthalmic disorders however the greasy nature of the ointments have led to patient non-compliance.[2] The high tear turnover of 16% per minute on the corneal surface allows only 1-10 percent of topically applied dose to be absorbed thus enhancing the frequency of administration required for completely alleviating the symptoms of the disease condition.[3] Novel drug delivery systems like in-situ gels, collagen shields, nanoparticles, liposomes, etc have been explored. However the high costs and complex manufacturing procedures limits the use of these systems. [4,5]

Keratoconjunctivitis sicca or Dry eye syndrome can be termed as a multifactorial disease of the tears and ophthalmic surface resulting in symptoms of tear film instability, visual disturbance and discomfort.[6] The symptoms are mainly due to inflammation of ophthalmic surface and increase in osmolarity of tear film.[7] The tear film performs several important functions like lubrication of ophthalmic surface and eyelids, supply of nutrients to ophthalmic surface, removal of microbes and foreign materials from the ophthalmic surface, protection against pathogens, provision of smooth ophthalmic surface for the eye and promotion of tissue maintenance and wound healing of ophthalmic surface.[8,9] The tear film is composed of three main layers, the mucous component forms the innermost layer which is responsible for lubrication of the ophthalmic surface as well as provides an adsorptive interface between hydrophobic corneal epithelium and aqueous layer. The middle layer is aqueous layer which comprises of water, electrolytes and antibacterial proteins. The outermost layer is the lipid layer which performs important functions like enhancing tear film spreading, slowing tear evaporation, preventing tear overflow etc.[10]

Dry eye disease is mainly classified as Aqueous Deficient Type and Evaporative Type based on the pathophysiological conditions causing the same.[11] Evaporative dry eye disease is mainly caused by Meibomian gland diseases, blink disorders, ophthalmic disorders, eyelid aperture disorders etc. [12] Continuous exposure to video display terminals like computer, television etc, air pollution, nutritional deficiency of Vitamin A and Omega fatty acids also form some crucial risk factors for Evaporative dry eye conditions.[13] Artificial tear formulations containing Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, Hyaluronic acid and other viscosity building polymers have been commonly used in soothing dry eye symptoms. However a high frequency of instillation is required for such preparations owing to rapid drainage and high tear turn over. [14]

Due to the sensitive anatomical features of eye and observed complexities of conventional ophthalmic dosage forms, there is a need for a suitable system to deliver poorly-soluble drugs in keratoconjunctivitis sicca with desirable soothing and anti-inflammatory activity.

Cationic submicron emulsions comprising of oil globules of submicronic size range possessing a positive charge have been explored as colloidal drug targeting systems in different pathophysiologies. The charged nature and submicronic size enhances the emulsion stability. Placebo cationic submicron emulsions have been explored as artificial tear systems where the aqueous dispersed phase aids to lubricate the inflamed ophthalmic surface and lower the irritation whereas the cationic submicronic globules get electrostatically attracted to negatively charged corneal membrane thus showing enhanced retention of the emulsion on the ophthalmic surface.[15,16]

Loteprednol etabonate, a topical corticoid anti-inflammatory drug is used in ophthalmic formulations for treating inflammatory conditions like dry eye syndrome, allergic conjunctivitis, iritis etc.[17] Its poor solubility makes its delivery using various conventional drug formulation approaches difficult. The present research work focusses on formulation and optimization of a stable cationic submicron emulsion that can be used to deliver poorly-soluble Loteprednol etabonate. The formulated cationic submicron emulsion containing Loteprednol etabonate was evaluated for its efficacy against Loteflam ® eyedrops (0.5% Loteprednol etabonate) in moderately evaporative dry eye rabbit models.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Loteprednol etabonate was gifted by Ajanta Pharma Limited, Mumbai India. Labrafac Lipophile WL 1349 was procured from Gattefosse India private Ltd, India. Solutol HS 15, Lutrol F68 and Cremaphor EL were gifted by BASF Mumbai, India. Lecithin was supplied as gift sample by Vav Life Sciences Mumbai, India. Stearylamine and Oleylamine were gifted by Shree Sai Industries, Mumbai. Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) was gifted by Colorcon, Mumbai, India. Cetrimide was purchased from Westcoast Laboratory Mumbai, India. Glycerine and Alpha-tocopherol were purchased from SD Fine chemicals Mumbai, India. All other chemicals used were analytical grade.

6 New Zealand White female rabbits weighing 2.5-3kg were purchased from Haffkine Institute Worli, Mumbai, India. IAEC approved protocol numbered ICT/IAEC/0910/22 was procured before the studies. Rabbits were housed in separate cages and environmental conditions were monitored to ensure suitability to rabbit housing. Humidity and temperature conditions of the animal house were maintained such that no interference is observed to dry eye studies.

Formulation and optimization of cationic submicronic emulsion

The placebo submicronic emulsion was formulated using homogenization method [18]. The formulation was optimized using Formulas I-V in order to arrive at the final optimized formula V yielding a stable homogenous submicron emulsion. [Table 1]. Formula V for stable cationic emulsion was considered for further drug incorporation studies. Oleylamine and alpha-tocopherol were weighed and added to Labrafac lipophilic WL 1349. The obtained oil phase was then stirred with slight heating at 40°C. 0.2 % w/w Loteprednol etabonate drug was added to this oily phase. 10% of the total aqueous phase was used to solubilize Cremaphor EL, Solutol HS 15, Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) and glycerine. The system was stirred with slight heating at 40°C to 55°C. Both phases were heated to a constant temperature of 65°C. The aqueous phase was added to the oil phase and stirred for 45 min at 75°C. Cetrimide was added to remaining aqueous phase and heated at 75°C. Cetrimide containing aqueous phase was added to the coarse emulsion and the resultant system was stirred at 75°C for 25min to obtain the final emulsion. The globule size of the emulsion was further decreased by high speed homogenization for 15 min and the emulsion was brought to 25°C. [19].

Table-1: Formulas I to V for Cationic submicron emulsion and formula V with Loteprednol etabonate drug.

Formula No → Ingredients↓	I	II	III	IV	V	V (with Loteprednol etabonate)
Medium chain Triglyceride	2	2	2	2	2	2
Lecithin	0.1	-	-	-	-	-
Solutol HS 15	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Lutrol F68	0.5	0.5	-	-	-	-
Stearylamine	0.1	-	-	-	-	-
Oleylamine	-	0.1	0.1	0.25	0.25	0.25
Cremaphor EL	-	-	0.5	1	1	1
HPMC	-	-	-	-	0.2	0.2
Cetrimide	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005
Alpha Tocopherol	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Glycerine	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.25
Loteprednol etabonate	-	-	-	-	-	0.2
Distilled Water (% w/w)	q.s. 100	q.s 100				

Pharmaceutical Evaluation Studies

pH:

pH of the cationic emulsion was determined by taking 30 ml of emulsion in a 50ml beaker and the pH was recorded at 25°C using a Standardized Sienna pH meter model no-UPH1.

Specific gravity:

Specific gravity of the formulation was measured using specific gravity bottle of 10 ml capacity using purified distilled water as a standard and was calculated using the following formula;

Specific gravity of the formulation= weight of 10ml of the formulation/weight of 10ml distilled water.

Viscosity:

Viscosity of the cationic emulsion was determined using Ostwald's capillary viscometer. Purified distilled water was used as a standard and the viscosity was measured at constant temperature of 25°C. Viscosity was calculated by using following formula;

$$\eta_1/\eta_2 = \rho_1 t_1 / \rho_2 t_2$$

where,

η_1 = viscosity of the emulsion,

η_2 = viscosity of the distilled water at 20°C i.e. 1.0086,

ρ_1 = specific gravity of the emulsion,

ρ_2 = Specific gravity of distilled water at 20°C,

t_1 = Time taken by emulsion in seconds,

t_2 = time taken by distilled water in seconds.

Osmolarity:

Osmolarity of the cationic emulsion were measured using digital osmometer model number 3250 by Advanced Instruments Inc. Osmolarity was measured as a direct reading considering 287 mOsm as the standard.

Globule size:

One drop of emulsion was taken in a clean test tube and diluted with 0.22 μ filtered Millipore water (Milli-Q, Millipore corp., USA) till a transparent solution was formed and the particle size was measured at 90⁰ angle on Beckman coulter N4 Plus submicron particle size analyser.

Zeta potential analysis:

Zeta potential of the emulsion was measured by using Malvern 2000 zetasizer. The sample of emulsion was diluted in Millipore water (Milli-Q, Millipore corp., USA) and injected in zeta cell. Each sample was analysed thrice, each analysis comprised of 100 runs of the instrument. The measurements were made in fully automatic mode.

Surface tension:

The surface tension of the continuous phase of emulsion was measured using Wilhelmy plate method taking water as a standard.

Drug content:

For the determination of drug content, emulsion equivalent containing 10 mg drug was dissolved in sufficient quantity of ethanol and volume was made up to 10 ml in volumetric flask with ethanol and absorbance measurement was done using Ultraviolet spectroscopy at λ -max 245nm using standard plot of Loteprednol etabonate in ethanol.

Physical Stability evaluation:

The emulsion was subjected to stability studies at various temperatures i.e. at room temperature (25°C-27°C), 4°C and in light. Emulsion stability to autoclaving was evaluated by placing the emulsion in a lab scale autoclave at 15 psi at the temperature of 121°C for 15 minutes. The stability of emulsion to centrifugation was evaluated by centrifuging it for 15 minutes at 5000-7000rpm. Stability of emulsion to freeze-thawing was evaluated by subjecting the emulsion to three freeze thaw cycles. Each cycle comprised of placing the emulsion containing container at 4°C for 2 days followed by placing the same at room temperature for 2 days and all emulsion formulations were observed for phase separation, flocculation or creaming after the completion of study.[20]

Pharmacological evaluation studies**Ocular irritation study**

Draize eye irritation test as per OECD guideline No 405(2) was performed on rabbits to evaluate the irritation potential of the cationic submicron emulsion. The test was based on determining the presence of ocular pathophysiological changes like corneal opacity, congestion, swelling of iris, haemorrhage, destruction of iris, chemosis, reddening of conjunctiva (hyperemia), mucosal discharge, moistening of eyelids and hair etc. in rabbit eyes after instillation of the emulsion. For the evaluation of present formulation, the emulsion formulation was instilled in the rabbit eyes and the eyes were observed at duration of 0, 12, 24, 48 and 72 hrs for presence of above pathophysiological conditions. The observation were made using Canon power shot digital camera.[21]

Dry eye induction in rabbits:

Rabbits were induced with dry eye by administration of 2 drops of 0.2% Benzalkonium chloride (BAC) solution twice a day for two days. Two days of topical instillation was found to be suitable for inducing the inflammatory symptoms and decreasing the tear production to produce moderate dry eye without causing permanent damage to the rabbit eye. The dry eye animal model produced by above procedure resembled the evaporative dry eye state in humans.[22]

Schirmer I tear test was used to measure tear production from rabbit eyes in both healthy and dry eye state. A small strip of Whatmann 41 filter paper of dimensions; 35×5mm is placed inside the lower conjunctival sac after sterilization after making a notch of 5mm from one end of the the strip for 5 minutes and the wetted length is measured after 5 minutes. The presence of the dry eye symptoms were observed by digital camera. The inflammatory symptoms produced were photographed.[23]

Treatment with submicronic emulsion containing Loteprednol etabonate:

After induction of dry eye in rabbits, the treatment of the rabbit was initiated by instilling Loteprednol etabonate containing emulsion twice a day. The efficacy of the emulsion was compared to Loteflam eye drops (0.5% Loteprednol etabonate) which were considered as positive control. Post-instillation of the formulation, the gradual changes in the various components of inflammatory symptoms like reddening of conjunctiva (bulbar and tarsal) and iris, conjunctival hyperemia, mucosal discharge, wetting of eyelids, hairs and surrounding regions of the eye, tearing and the ease of opening of eyes of rabbits were photographed and increase in tear production volume was measured. The rise in tear production from day one of instillation was measured. The treatment was continued till the treated eye was normalized to a healthy state with complete absence of inflammatory symptoms and the tear reading normalized to basal values. The rise in tear production by developed cationic submicron emulsion containing 0.2% Loteprednol etabonate from day one of instillation was compared to that of Loteflam® eyedrops containing 0.5% Loteprednol etabonate (positive control). A two-ways ANOVA test was applied to compare the efficacy of the emulsion formulation against positive control Loteflam® 0.5% eyedrops.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Formulation studies:

Emulsion prepared using formulas I to IV were found to show creaming and non-homogenous appearance. Formula V was found to show homogenous non-creamy appearance hence it was considered for incorporation of Loteprednol etabonate. Opaque white and milky homogeneous emulsion with no creamy layer was obtained when 0.2% w/w Loteprednol etabonate was incorporated in Formula V. [Fig 1] No phase separation was observed.

Fig.-1: Homogenous non-creamy emulsion containing 0.2% Loteprednol etabonate obtained by drug incorporation in Optimised formula V.

Pharmaceutical evaluation studies:

pH:

The emulsion containing Loteprednol etabonate was found to show pH of 7.22 which was close to the pH of normal tear fluid. Drug incorporation in cationic submicron emulsion was not found to alter the emulsion pH. The desirable pH for topical ophthalmic formulations to be instilled in eye without causing any irritation to corneal milieu is pH close to 7.

Specific gravity:

The specific gravity of the Loteprednol etabonate containing emulsion was found to be 1.004.

Viscosity:

Loteprednol etabonate containing emulsion was found to show a viscosity of 2.41 mPa.s compatible to ophthalmic milieu. An ophthalmic formulation with viscosity of 1.3 to 5.9 is considered compatible to corneal tissue with desirable retention on the eye surface.

Globule size:

The globule size of the Loteprednol etabonate containing cationic submicron emulsion formulation was found to be 978 nm. The submicronic size of globules act as drug carriers and support the colloidal targeting of the drug. Submicronic size of the globules also aids to enhance the stability of cationic emulsion.

Zeta potential:

The Loteprednol etabonate containing cationic submicron emulsion was found to show a positive zeta potential of 67.4 mV confirming the cationic nature of the dispersed oil phase. The zeta potential of the emulsion is an indicative property of emulsion stability and is influenced by the nature of cationic lipid used and the surfactant and stabilizer systems present in the formulation.

Osmolarity:

Osmolarity of the Loteprednol etabonate containing cationic submicron emulsion was found to be 286 milliOsm. The cationic submicron emulsion was found to show desirable osmolarity as the osmolarity values desirable for an ophthalmic formulation between 293 to 288 milliOsm. Higher osmolarity values of tear fluid is observed in dry eye syndrome mostly 308 milliOsm. One of the reasons for the occurrence of inflammatory symptoms is the rise in the osmolarity values of the tear fluid.

Surface tension:

Surface tension of tear fluid is found to be between to be 44 to 50mN/m. The surface tension of distilled water was found to be 40mN/m. The use of emulsifier in the emulsion formulation was found to lower the surface tension value of continuous phase to 38 mN/m. thus aiding to give a formulation with enhanced wetting of dry corneal surface.

Drug Content:

The cationic emulsion was found to contain 94% Loteprednol etabonate.

Stability testing:

No cracking and phase separation was observed in the cationic emulsion at different temperature conditions like 4°C, 25°C and exposure to light. The formulation was found to be stable to autoclaving, centrifugation and freeze thaw cycling conditions.

Pharmacological Evaluation studies:**Ocular Irritation Study**

No pathophysiological changes like corneal opacity, congestion, swelling, haemorrhage, destruction of iris, chemosis, reddening of conjunctiva, mucosal discharge, moistening of eyelids and hairs (indicative of inflammation) were observed after 0, 12, 24, 48, and 72 hrs of topical instillation of formulation thus indicating the formulation to be safe for ophthalmic use.

Development of dry eye model in rabbits:

Inflammation of bulbar and tarsal conjunctiva, swelling of eyelid membrane, mucosal discharge and wetting of regions surrounding the eyes, and difficulties in closing eyes was distinctly observed.[Fig 2(a-d)] The tear production was found to decrease from 17 mm to 8 mm as measured by Schirmer I Tear Test.

Fig 2(a-d):2a) Inflammation of bulbar and tarsal conjunctiva 2b) swelling of eyelid membrane 2c) wetting of regions surrounding the eyes 2d) Difficult eye closure.

Treatment of dry eyes of rabbit model with Loteprednol etabonate emulsion:

Instillation of the Loteprednol etabonate containing cationic emulsion twice a day was found to show reduction in the various inflammatory symptoms of reddening of conjunctiva (bulbar and tarsal), conjunctival hyperemia, mucosal discharge from the eye, wetting of eyelids, hairs and surrounding regions, tearing and difficult opening of eyes. 3 days of topical instillation of the developed cationic submicron emulsion against positive control was found to show complete alleviation of all inflammatory symptoms and normalisation of eye closure [Fig 3]. Statistically significant results were obtained for measurement of increase in tear readings after emulsion instillation with P value of 0.0001 ($P < 0.05$).

Thus the developed cationic submicron emulsion containing lower concentration of Loteprednol etabonate i.e. 0.2% w/w was found to show comparable efficacy as marketed Loteflam® eyedrops containing 0.5% w/w Loteprednol etabonate drug.

Fig 3 : Daywise observations of alleviation of inflammatory symptoms in dry eye rabbit models after instillation of cationic submicron emulsion containing 0.2 % Loteprednol etabonate and Loteflam® 0.5 % eyedrops.

CONCLUSION

The frequent exposure to Computers, video display terminals, environmental pollution, dysfunctioning of secretory lacrimal glands etc have led to increased occurrence of inflammatory ophthalmic conditions like Keratoconjunctivitis sicca. Artificial tear formulations used commonly to alleviate the symptoms are required to be instilled frequently thus increasing patient non-compliance giving rise to need for topical formulations with higher residence time on the ophthalmic surface.

In the present work, a cationic submicronic emulsion, with potential to incorporate both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drug molecules in their aqueous and oily phase was formulated and evaluated for efficacy as a drug delivery system for poorly soluble anti-inflammatory drug Loteprednol etabonate. The judicious selection of cationic lipid, stabilizing surfactants and the use of Medium chain triglyceride as the oily phase led to development of a cationic submicronic system containing lower concentration of drug Loteprednol etabonate i.e. 0.2% which was found to show good efficacy as a topical soothing drug delivery vehicle comparable to marketed drug formulation Loteflam® eyedrops (0.5% Loteprednol etabonate) when evaluated in moderate dry eye rabbit models of evaporative type. Cationic submicron emulsion was found to be a prospective colloidal drug delivery system in keratoconjunctivitis sicca. It can be further explored to deliver poorly-soluble drugs with versatile therapeutic targets at lower concentration and consequently lowered toxicity in several ophthalmic pathophysiologies.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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